

Empowerment Through Education: Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's Vision for Social Equality and Justice

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Abstract:

This study focuses on Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's perspectives on Education and his conviction in the principles of education, unity, and struggle. Ambedkar recognised that education is the most effective tool to eradicate social oppression and empower marginalised individuals to achieve social advancement, economic improvement, and political liberation. Education played a crucial role as a prerequisite for societal reconstruction based on the principles of equality and justice. Upon examining the evolution of education within Indian society, it was seen that the entitlement to education was limited to individuals belonging to higher castes, both under the reign of Peshwa in Maharashtra and in the earlier era of the British Raj. He advocated for universal education, regardless of caste and gender. The individual expressed their involvement in the budgetary deliberation, asserting that education should be made accessible to all individuals. The education department cannot be approached with a quid pro quo approach.

Education should be made more affordable by various means and to the maximum extent feasible. He actively participated in the deliberation over the Bombay University Act and the Primary Education Amendment Bill, offering his perspectives on educational reform. The individual established the People's Education Society and initiated educational institutions in Bombay and Aurangabad. He consistently emphasised to the government that it must ensure equal educational chances for all individuals, without any form of bias. However, he argued that boys and girls should receive distinct educational experiences. This paper aims to explore Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's perspectives on education, specifically focusing on the implementation of a uniform education system in India.

Key Words: Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, the right to education, Article 21A, economic uplift, Dalits, education, social uplift, marginalized people etc.

Introduction

Ambedkar espoused the belief that education constituted the major avenue for elevating the socioeconomic status of individuals. His catchphrase was "Educate, unite, struggle." The initial term of his renowned slogan is "Educate."

Ambedkar's scholarly contributions to education encompass his testimony presented before the Indian Statutory Commission in the Bombay Presidency regarding the "State of Education of the Dalits." The deposition in question is included in the compilation titled "Dr. Ambedkar: Sampoorana Vangmay" specifically in Volume 4. Furthermore, his article entitled

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"Subsidy for Education" has been incorporated into Dr Ambedkar: Sampoorna Vangmay (Volume 3). This article is derived from his address to the Bombay Legislative Council on 12 March 1927, where he advocated for augmented government funding for education and emphasised the necessity of affordable education for marginalised communities. The book "Dr Ambedkar: Sampoorna Vangmay" (Volume 19) addresses several problems of the Scheduled Castes (SCs), including their apprehensions regarding education.

The issues can be categorised into two sections: "insufficient support for higher education" and "inadequate resources for technical training".

Struggle of Ambedkar for Dalit's Education

The topic of freedom often overlooks the significance of Dalit freedom. Shortly, we will commemorate the anniversary of our liberation from British colonial rule. Now is an opportune moment to address the issue of Dalit freedom. The Dalits were subjected to a system of double slavery, which was ultimately liberated by Ambedkar. The British Government, deeply influenced by Gandhiji's Civil Disobedience Movement, organised a Round Table Conference in London on November 12, 1930. At the convention, a youthful attorney astonished everyone by declining to recognise Gandhiji as the supreme leader of the entire Indian population. According to him, the majority of Congress officials held the belief in caste-based prejudice and were unwilling to grant Dalits any participation in constitutional procedures. Hence, he posited that the establishment of distinct electorates, exclusively comprising Dalit candidates and electors, was imperative.

British Prime Minister Ramsay Macdonald declared the Communal Award on 6 August 1932, which acknowledged the Dalits as separate from the Hindus and established a separate electorate for them. During that period, Mahatma Gandhi was detained in the Poona prison. He perceived this revelation as a plot to estrange Dalits from the Hindu community. On September 20, 1932, Mahatma Gandhi initiated a fast-unto-death as a form of protest against the Communal Award, causing significant unrest in the nation. A call was made to Dr Ambedkar to preserve the life of Mahatma Gandhi. In response to mounting pressure from various factions, Ambedkar acquiesced to a compromise, contingent upon the provision of reservations for the Dalits across all societal strata. Gandhiji consented and thereafter ceased his fast on the 26th of September.

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During the latter part of the 19th century, social reformers initiated a vehement critique of Brahmanical rites using their literary works. Gulamgiri, authored by Jotirao Phule, was among them. Periyar and Narayan Guru expressed their opposition to the Varna system in the southern region. Several decades later, Ambedkar was entrusted with the task of formulating the Constitution of the recently emancipated India, acknowledging his exceptional qualifications and scholarly contributions. He assumed the position of the nation's inaugural law minister. Subsequently, Ambedkar's ideas have gained increasing significance throughout time.

Before achieving independence, he was acknowledged as a jurist possessing exceptional intellectual abilities. During his speech before the Bombay Legislative Council on 12 March 1927, he posed relevant inquiries regarding education in Indian society. The individual expressed profound apprehension regarding India's educational deficiency.

A report published by the Government of India, it was stated that if the current pace of educational advancement continues, it would require 40 years for boys and 300 years for girls of school-going age to receive education. Dr. Ambedkar expressed concern over the conflicting objectives of two departments within the presidency. The Department of Education serves the objective of fostering moral and social development among individuals. Conversely, we have the Department of Excise that is operating oppositely. Sir, I believe it is reasonable to request that we allocate an equivalent amount of funds to education as we currently get from the public through excise income. The per capita expenditure on education in this presidency amounts to a mere 14 annas, whereas the corresponding excise revenue generated amounts to Rs 2.17 [35 annas]. I believe it is equitable that our educational spending should be proportionate to the amount we receive from the people in the form of taxation.[1] In the present day, as not just students but also other groups advocating for change are advocating for increased funding for education, Ambedkar's ideas can provide us with valuable guidance.

Dr Ambedkar raised another concern during the debate, stating that the current allocation of funds towards basic education is largely squandered. The basic objective of primary education is to ensure that each child who joins a primary school attains literacy skills and maintains literacy throughout their lifetime. However, after analysing the data, it becomes evident that only eighteen out of every hundred children who start primary school successfully

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achieve the fourth grade. The remaining 82 children, or 82 out of every 100, go back to a state of illiteracy.[2]

The issue of school dropouts remains unresolved. Dr Ambedkar had previously comprehended this issue. The individual came to the realisation that only sending a child to school was insufficient. It is crucial to ensure their continued attendance in school till they have completed their primary education. The act of just planting a seedling is insufficient. Additionally, it is imperative to provide it with adequate water and fertilisers to prevent premature mortality. Hence, Ambedkar expressed his plea to the esteemed education minister to allocate additional funds towards basic education, to ensure that their expenditure yields tangible outcomes.

Dr Ambedkar also focused on the phenomenon of commoditization in the field of education. He stated that upon reviewing the data regarding the funding of education in this presidency, it is evident that approximately 36 per cent of the total expenses for art colleges, 31 per cent of the expenses for high schools, and 26 per cent of the expenses for middle schools are funded through fees. It can be asserted that the phenomenon being referred to is the commercialization of education. The accessibility of education should be ensured for all individuals. Due to Dr. Ambedkar's profound concern for the lower socioeconomic groups, he stated, "We are currently at a point where the lower classes are just beginning to attend high schools, middle schools, and colleges. Therefore, this department must ensure that higher education is as affordable as possible for the lower classes."

He references another significant concern: The census report of this administration has categorised the entire population into four distinct classes to compare the progress of various communities in terms of education." The initial category is referred to as "advanced Hindus", whereas the subsequent category is known as "intermediate Hindus". This category encompasses those who, for political reasons, have been officially classified as non-Brahmins, specifically Marathas and associated castes. A distinct category known as the backward classes encompasses those belonging to the depressed classes, Hill Tribes, and Criminal Tribes. Subsequently, the fourth category pertains to the Mahomedans. Taking into consideration these differences, it becomes evident that there exists a significant disparity in the relative progress of these distinct communities about education. Dr. Ambedkar's primary focus revolved around

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the inequities that permeated Indian society. According to his statement, the nation is comprised of diverse communities. These towns exhibit disparities in terms of their social standing and advancement. From an economic and sociological perspective, it can be argued that backward classes experience unique disadvantages that distinguish them from other communities. Hence, I believe that the principle of preferential treatment should be implemented in their situation. As demonstrated, the status of the Mahomedans is comparatively inferior to that of the backward classes. My sole argument is that if preferential care is to be granted to those who are deserving and in greatest need, then the Mahomedans should receive less attention from the Government.

Thus, Dr. Ambedkar's perspectives on education were congruent with the geographical, social, and economic context of India, and were grounded in scientific rationale.

Struggle with Unity and Education

The scholarly examination of Dr. Ambedkar's perspectives on education remains limited, despite his extensive involvement in the field of education since the establishment of the Hitkarini Sabha in 1924. One of the aims of the Sabha was to ensure that an increasing number of underprivileged classes received education. To do this, the Sabha created several colleges, hostels, libraries, and reading centres. The students, under the leadership of the Sabha, initiated the launch of a monthly publication called Saraswati Belas. In 1935, the Sabha founded hostels in Sholapur and Belgaun, as well as a free reading centre, a hockey club, and two hostels in Bombay. The Depressed Classes Educational Society was established by Dr. Ambedkar in 1928. In 1945, he established the Lok Shaikshik Samaj to ensure access to higher education for the underprivileged sections. The aforementioned organisation initiated the establishment of several colleges and middle schools. Additionally, it provided financial aid to hostels. In summary, the Lok Shaikshik Samaj played a significant role in facilitating the accessibility of higher education for the Dalit community.

Dr. Ambedkar's literary works encompassed a wide range of subjects, including economics, law, the Constitution, political science, sociology, philosophy, religion, anthropology, and more. Furthermore, his enduring fascination with education was evident. It extended beyond mere speculation. He made efforts to articulate his perspectives pragmatically.

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The initial term of his renowned slogan is "Educate." The unquestionable significance of education lies in its function in shaping human character and consciousness. Class unity can only be achieved by an individual who possesses a high level of education and comprehends their class interests. Education leads an individual onto a road of adversity. According to Dr Ambedkar, education has a crucial role in fostering fearlessness, imparting the value of togetherness, cultivating awareness of one's rights, and motivating individuals to actively advocate for their rights. He had the belief that education is a dynamic progress. If it fails to achieve its goals, it becomes futile. Dr. Ambedkar explicitly asserted that an education lacking the ability to empower individuals and impart principles of equality and morality is not genuine education. Authentic education nurtures the human race, creates avenues for sustenance, conveys knowledge, and fosters a sense of equality. Genuine education invigorates society.

Objectives of Education

The social-philosophical perspectives of Ambedkar were founded upon the principle of egalitarianism. His social thought revolved around the principles of human dignity and self-respect. His objective was to utilise education as a means to develop principles of justice, equality, fraternity, freedom, and fearlessness within society. He desired to substitute a society based on birth with one based on values. Undoubtedly, education is the sole means by which these moral principles can be advanced.

Ambedkar's philosophical framework was profoundly shaped by Buddhist principles, and he espoused the cultivation of moral values among individuals. According to his statement, the significance of education lies solely in its ability to contribute to the well-being and prosperity of individuals, as well as the advancement of society. He also advocated for aligning education with employment. Education is crucial in fostering societal stability. Exemplary behaviour and proper conduct stem from rational thinking, which can only be attained through formal education, practical experience, and meaningful conversations. The educational goals of Ambedkar were congruent with his broader social, economic, and political aspirations. He exhibited a firm advocacy for the principles of logical and scientific education.

As the deadline neared, the education minister at the time, MC Chagla, remarked: "Our Constitutional framers did not intend for us to simply establish slums, place students there, assign unqualified teachers, provide them with inadequate textbooks, and lack playgrounds,

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and claim that we have adhered to Article 45 and that primary education is growing... According to MC Chagla (1964), they intended to provide genuine education to youngsters aged 6 to 14 which can be found in the Right to Education Act (RTE).

The Right to Education Act (RTE), also known as the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, is a legislative measure passed by the Parliament of India on August 4, 2009. This act outlines the significance of providing free and compulsory education to children aged 6 to 14 in India, as mandated by Article 21a of the Indian Constitution. India joined the ranks of 135 nations that have established education as an essential entitlement for every child, following the implementation of the Act on 1 April 2010.

The legislation establishes education as an essential entitlement for all children aged 6 to 14 and outlines the basic standards for primary schools. Private schools are obligated to allocate 25% of their seats for children, with the state providing reimbursement as part of the public-private partnership strategy. Children are admitted to private schools based on their economic level or reservations based on caste. Additionally, it forbids the operation of any schools that have not been officially recognised, and stipulates that there will be no payments for donations or capitation, and no interviews will be conducted with the child or parent for admittance. According to the Act, it is prohibited to detain, expel, or mandate a board examination for any child until they have finished primary education. Additionally, a framework exists for the implementation of specialised training programmes aimed at bringing school dropouts up to the level of their peers of the same age.

Education is a potent instrument by which those who are economically and socially disadvantaged can uplift themselves from poverty and actively engage as members of society.

India harbours 19% of the global population of children. This implies that India possesses the highest population of young individuals globally, a predominantly advantageous circumstance, particularly when juxtaposed with nations such as China, which exhibit a progressively ageing populace. Regrettably, India also possesses one-third of the global population without literacy skills. Literacy levels have increased, but the rate of this increase is significantly decelerating. As an illustration, the overall increase in literacy from 1991 to 2001 was 12.6%, but it has already decreased to 9.21%.

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Currently, there are legal avenues available to hold the state responsible for its interpretation of student 'rights'. Nevertheless, as previously mentioned, these places alone are inadequate to offer influence, and additionally only acknowledge the rights of those who are already 'included'. Education guarantee schemes, such as the one currently implemented in Madhya Pradesh (and now a nationwide commitment under the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, a new policy aimed at universalizing elementary education), aim to provide schools in underserved areas that have a demand for them. However, it is important to note that the type of schools, their quality, and the content they offer are not subject to citizen action and are exclusively regulated by the state. As donor financing towards the state continues to rise and efforts are made to centralise policy spaces through sector and sub-sector approaches, there is a potential danger of strengthening the state's control over civil society and other organisations, while also diminishing transparency. NGOs have played a significant role in advancing education, particularly in recent years. However, many of their educational models are being directly incorporated into state programmes without a thorough examination of the benefits and insights they offer in developing localised education strategies that prioritise community ownership. Despite the growing use of the term 'community involvement' in state projects, there is a lack of efforts to tackle the underlying causes of inequality that hinder the most marginalised people from voicing their opinions (see Subrahmanian, forthcoming). Village Education Committees (VECs), which are widely recognised as a novel manifestation of community engagement in education, frequently exhibit bureaucratic characteristics that prioritise the task of identifying and escorting children to school, rather than actively seeking parental input on educational content and delivery.

Right to Education Act

The implementation of Article 21-A and the Right to Education Act commenced on April 1, 2010. The phrase 'free and compulsory' is included in the title of the Right to Education (RTE) Act. The term 'free education' refers to the provision that no child, except for those admitted by their parents to a school that lacks support from the relevant government, will be required to pay any fees, charges, or expenses that could hinder their ability to pursue and finish elementary education. The concept of 'compulsory education' imposes a responsibility on the relevant governmental and municipal entities to guarantee the provision, attendance, and successful completion of primary education for all children between the ages of 6 and 14. India

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has progressed towards a system based on rights, which imposes a legal duty on both the Central and State Governments to enforce the fundamental rights of children as outlined in Article 21A of the Constitution, along with the provisions of the Right to Education Act.

The RTE Act provides for the:

The entitlement of children to receive education that is both free and mandatory until they have completed their primary education at a local school.

The term 'compulsory education' refers to the responsibility of the relevant government to offer free primary education and guarantee mandatory entrance, attendance, and completion of elementary school for all children between the ages of six and fourteen. The term 'free' refers to the condition where no child is required to pay any fees, charges, or expenses that could hinder their ability to pursue and finish elementary education. It allows for the admission of a child who has not been admitted to a class that is suitable for their age.

The document delineates the obligations and roles of relevant governmental bodies, local authorities, and parents in ensuring the provision of education that is both free and mandatory. Additionally, it outlines the distribution of financial and other responsibilities between the Central and State Governments. The document establishes the regulations and criteria about several aspects, including pupil-pupil-teacher ratios (PTRs), physical facilities and infrastructure, school working days, and teacher working hours.

It facilitates the efficient allocation of teachers by guaranteeing that the designated pupil-to-teacher ratio is upheld for each school, rather than being based solely on the average for the State, District, or Block. This ensures that there is no disparity in teacher positions between urban and rural areas. Additionally, it includes provisions that ban the deployment of teachers for non-educational purposes, excluding activities such as conducting decennial censuses, participating in elections for local authorities, state legislatures, and parliament, as well as conducting disaster relief efforts. It facilitates the selection of suitably qualified teachers, specifically those who possess the necessary entry and academic credentials.

The legislation encompasses several provisions, including the prohibition of physical punishment and mental harassment, screening methods for child enrollment, capitation fees, private tuition by teachers, and the operation of schools without recognition.

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The curriculum is designed to align with the values outlined in the Constitution and promote the comprehensive development of the child. It aims to enhance the child's knowledge, potential, and talent, while also ensuring their freedom from fear, trauma, and anxiety. This is achieved through a child-friendly and child-centred learning system.

Conclusion

Each successive generation aspires to the succeeding generation with the aspiration that they will construct a nation that surpasses the current state. Hence, any nation must prioritise education as a means of empowering the forthcoming generation. It is widely acknowledged that the realisation of the right to education at a national level is contingent upon the implementation of compulsory education, specifically through the provision of free obligatory elementary school. Nevertheless, the endeavour to establish an educational system in India that ensures comprehensive access, equality, and high-quality education has not been realised, mostly due to the pervasive poverty and societal biases. The lack of ability to assess dropout rates within marginalised populations is an additional source of concern.

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